

Deliverable D2.3 1st Report on delivered data management and stewardship courses

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE: Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services (871075)		
Project Acronym (EC Call):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE (H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020)		
WP No & Title:	WP2 Training and Capacity Building		
WP leader(s):	Celia van Gelder (DTL-Projects), Alexia Cardona (UCAM), Patricia Palagi (SIB), Brane Leskošek (UL)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	27 - UL		
Contractual delivery date:	31/01/2022	Actual delivery date:	13/06/2022
Delayed:	Yes		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	BE, CH, CZ, DE, EE, EMBL-EBI, ES, FI, FR, GR, HU, IE, IL,IT, LU, NL, NO, PT, SE, SI, UK (nodes represented by WP2 partners listed in alphabetical order)		
<p>Authors: Brane Leskošek (UL), Alexia Cardona (UCAM), Celia van Gelder (DTL-Projects), Patricia Palagi (SIB)</p> <p>Contributors: All WP2 members</p> <p>Other contributors: /</p> <p>Acknowledgments (not grant participants): /</p>			
Reviewers:	ELIXIR-CONVERGE Management Board (MB) members.		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
20/05/2022	0v1	Brane Leskošek (UL)	Initial version
20/5/2022	0v2	Brane Leskošek (UL)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
25/05/2022	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
08/06/2022	0v4	Brane Leskošek (UL)	MB comments addressed

13/06/2022	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version uploaded into EC Portal
------------	-----	------------------------------	---------------------------------------

Table of contents

Executive Summary	1
Contribution toward project objectives	2
Introduction	4
Relationship with other WPs	5
Description of work accomplished	6
Results	7
Delivered training events	7
Matching training events topics with identified training gaps	9
Conclusions	11
Impact	12
Next Steps	13
Deviation from Description of Action	13

1. Executive Summary

The scope of this deliverable is to report on the delivered training events across ELIXIR Nodes related to Data Management (DM) and Data Stewardship (DS). The delivered training events include both reruns of existing Node courses (that address the identified DM/DS training needs and gaps), as well as new courses developed in Task 2.2. This report provides an overview of the delivered DM/DS training events according to the ELIXIR-CONVERGE roadmap.

71 courses organised by 16 Countries/Nodes with more than 2000 participants **were delivered** in the observed period from Feb 2020 until Dec 2021. 41 of 71 courses have open-access training materials. Most frequently addressed topics were FAIR, Data Management Plans (DMPs), Data Management & Data Stewardship (DM/DS) and Reproducibility. Significantly more courses were about FAIR and DMP than Reproducibility and DM/DS. The materials for these topics will be consolidated and developed further in specific training hackathons (Task 2.2), similarly the T2.3 will help with identification of training needs and delivery of training solutions for Demonstrators (WP5, T5.4).

Activity of all four tasks of ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 are closely interwoven together and all participants of WP2 collaborate tightly. Thus, WP2 partners worked together to collect data about training events (Training Inventory, T2.1) and matched training events with 14 priority training gaps in DM/DS identified by gap analysis (D2.1). The identified gaps have kicked off collaborative development of high-quality training materials, developed by experts across ELIXIR and beyond (T2.2). The training hackathons that will be organised by T2.2 will provide more new training materials and courses. Task 2.3 has focused on delivered training events that were reported by ELIXIR Nodes and are based on both new and existing training materials. The outreach activity (T2.4) will disseminate training activities and courses to ELIXIR Communities and Nodes, as well as to countries that strive to become new ELIXIR members. We will continue to work towards the harmonisation and compilation of DM/DS training in ELIXIR.

The presented visualisation (Figures 2 and 3 in Chapter 5) will be continuously updated with new data in the Training Inventory in order to demonstrate how the delivery of DM/DS training events matches training gaps in the European ELIXIR network/community.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No

Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	Yes
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	Yes
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	Yes
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	Yes
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable ‘FAIR at source’ practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No

Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No
---	-----------

3. Introduction

There is a clear need for training of researchers on research data management (RDM) skills. ELIXIR-CONVERGE will improve Europe's data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area. The gap in RDM training has been widely acknowledged, for example in ELIXIR studies as well as within T2.1 of ELIXIR-CONVERGE:

- [ELIXIR Training Gap Analysis 2020 Survey](#)¹ (DM Training was identified as a one of priority gaps in the Training Platform gap analysis)
- [ELIXIR Implementation Study: Towards Data Stewardship in ELIXIR: Training & Portal](#).²
- ELIXIR-CONVERGE Deliverable D2.1 Report on identified training needs and a timeline for training courses³.

The overall objective of CONVERGE-WP2 is to build a comprehensive, interconnected and sustainable ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management. This is in line with Objective 2 (Strengthen Europe's data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area) of ELIXIR-CONVERGE by working towards:

- A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.
- Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.

The main target audiences are researchers and data stewards across all ELIXIR Nodes. We aim to develop and deliver a set of foundational ELIXIR Data Management courses. These courses will form part of the ELIXIR Data Management Training Portfolio. To harmonise the different ongoing training efforts, the courses developed and work done in WP2 will be in synergy with the existing ELIXIR Training Platform efforts and will make use of the Training Toolkit, the ELIXIR Training Metrics Database, the Quality & Impact strategy and TeSS (see Figure 1). Furthermore, the aim is to have all

¹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1LH46pICA0092O32xbru1dRM8g4kHeCe4/view?usp=sharing>

² <https://docs.google.com/document/d/18JGgTNCrOeEnCzHOIHwvmjlpacGp8rU4HPxWCM5t7oO/edit#heading=h.wwn5buq4rokg>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4892863>

training materials developed in WP2 as FAIR⁴ as possible to act as a blueprint for future sustainable courses developed in the ELIXIR Training Platform.

The Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management and Stewardship covers different types of training events:

- Training courses or workshops, with hands-on activities.
- Hackathons where participants collaborate to improve data management practices, and translate the results into new training materials.
- Training events for new trainers in data management and stewardship - Train-the-Trainer (TtT) events.

Relationship with other WPs

ELIXIR-CONVERGE aims to connect the distributed local support for data management in life sciences across Europe. The project uses three main resources:

- People: the network of data management professionals (WP1).
- Shared toolkit (RDMkit⁵): the tools and best practices (WP3) with the data from the Demonstrator Projects (WP5).
- Skills and training (WP2).

All three will be the drivers to improve data management skills via the DM Training Programme that will be set up by CONVERGE WP2.

WP2 connects with and supports the other CONVERGE WPs to identify their training-related needs and translate this into activities, which will enhance their end-products and increase their DM/DS expertise:

- **WP1** Data Management Experts network - to identify trainers/teachers among DM experts, and collect more information about training events for the training roadmap.
- **WP3** (T3.4 led by Pinar Alper, ELIXIR-LU) - to coordinate the training information required in the RDMkit. WP2 participated in **WP3** contentathons and established the training links and data steward roles in the RDMkit. RDMKit-TeSS links activity was started as collaboration between WP2 and WP3⁶. In addition, **WP2** has organised two hackathons to [register](#)⁷ and [annotate](#)⁸ WP2 materials in TeSS, and finalise the RDMKit-TeSS connections
- **WP4** - to identify speakers who could present the training efforts in events for ELIXIR communities and for countries interested in becoming ELIXIR Nodes. Both work packages will continue working together to establish dissemination materials.
- **WP5** - to establish use-case related training and work with T5.4 (lead by Brane Leskošek, ELIXIR-SI) to identify training needs for use-cases training events. The [training needs survey](#)⁹

⁴ Garcia L, Batut B, Burke ML, Kuzak M, Psomopoulos F, et al. (2020) Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. PLOS Computational Biology 16(5): e1007854. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007854>

⁵ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

⁶ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1z-iFns6_uua76jxvFveW8wKo74UxxcX6/edit#slide=id.p1

⁷ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1cg5wRx8Gr1TnUPMsw4_WV7e29eR0GeU1dlwDymEuifw/edit#slide=id.p1

⁸ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1sKfDq_FbU29ySn87OUK6ipCOnYL4v9YqUWWdxMiuqU4/edit#slide=id.p1

⁹ <https://elixir.mf.uni-lj.si/course/view.php?id=73>

was completed among demonstrator projects and received 9 answers from all 6 original demonstrator projects, now 1-2-1 interviews are in progress. The survey and interview results will provide better insights into training needs, and will help us develop and deliver target training events for selected demonstrator projects.

- **WP6** - to define the [ELIXIR Node Coordinators Curriculum](#)¹⁰.
- **Additional new WPs (WP7, WP8 and WP9)** related to the COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 data, tools and services.

The collaborations of WP2 extend beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE in order to bring additional expertise and knowledge to the DM/DS domain. Such collaborations could ensure better sustainability after ELIXIR-CONVERGE. Figure 1 shows the different stakeholders and collaborators involved in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 Training and Capacity building project and how WP2 is bringing all this together through its training efforts.

Figure 1: Stakeholders and Collaborators with ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 - Training and Capacity Building

¹⁰ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/118IGxN7T3JkciD7mfDNkgRrZifl1DwuZcsufaW3F5qA/edit>

4. Description of work accomplished

Participating Nodes were encouraged to deliver DM/DS training and capacity building events based on training needs and gaps identified in Task 2.1. Data on delivered training events were collected in the Training Inventory spreadsheet within the Training Events tab¹¹. The metadata collected in the Training Inventory includes (among others) contact person, title, target audience, target audience expertise level, dates and duration, number of participants, event format, links to course information and materials, as well as training event categories (course, workshop, hackathon, webinar). The collected metadata could serve as a source for the extension of the metadata data model in TeSS.

In addition, all Nodes that delivered training events were asked to provide information about the gaps that were covered by their events. There are 14 training gaps which were identified by gap analysis described in D2.1. The gap matching information was collected in separate columns in the Training Inventory spreadsheet. This information was analysed and visualised (see next chapter). All activities were done in close collaboration with tasks T2.1 and T2.2.

5. Results

Delivered training events

The observed period of training events delivery was from the beginning of CONVERGE in February 2020 to the end of December 2021. Numbers are presented in Figures 2 and 3 and Tables 1 to 3.

Figure 2: Summary of the training events delivered from Feb 2020 until Dec 2021.

¹¹ [WP2 Training Inventory](#)

Table 1 presents the distribution of delivered training events in 2020-21 among Nodes. In the observed period 71 training events were reported in the Training Inventory, many of them were co-branded between project partners and WP2. These training events were delivered by 16 ELIXIR Nodes (34 courses in 2020 and 37 courses in 2021). 16 Nodes delivered at least one event, out of 21 participating Nodes in CONVERGE WP2 (data source: [CONVERGE Project Proposal](#)¹²). The number of delivered courses with available training materials is also provided, together with the cumulative number of course participants. The number of training events with available materials across all Nodes was 40 (out of 71 delivered training events). 47 training events were attended by researchers (including young researchers), 14 training events for Data managers/Data stewards (DM/DS), 6 events for both DM/DS and researchers and 4 training events for other audiences (CONVERGE project participants or others). There were 2105 participants at all training events combined.

¹² <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1IZE6Wv0j5NOVpuPJRUDBTy4mcsbRgzUt>

Table 1: Number of delivered training events for each Node involved in CONVERGE WP2 in the period February 2020 until December 2021 and reported by January 2022 (data source: [WP2 Training Inventory and Roadmap](#)¹³)

ELIXIR Node	Number of delivered training events on DM/DS	Number of delivered DM/DS training events with available training materials	Cumulative number of participants at delivered DM/DS training events
BE	2	1	80
CH	3	0	56
CZ	19	13	804
DE	4	0	45
EE	3	3	28
EMBL-EBI	5	0	107
ES	6	4	165
FI	7	2	331
FR	4	4	72
GR	0	0	0
HU	0	0	0
IE	0	0	0
IL	1	0	not reported
IT	0	0	0
LU	1	1	100
NL	4	4	73
NO	2	2	85
PT	8	5	124
SE	1	1	15
SI	1	0	20
UK	0	0	0

¹³ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Vu-qzbJZOhKSJeUhzF4NDIUSDzZY7FPO8y2zDs-oDP4/edit#gid=1069928084>

Total	71	40	2105
--------------	-----------	-----------	-------------

Table 2 presents the observed training events split by the type (number of training courses with hands-on exercises, hackathons and Train-the-Trainer (TtT) events).

Table 2: Number of training courses, hackathons and TtT events delivered in 2020-21 and reported by January 2022.

Type of training event	Number of training events
Training courses with hands-on activities	65
Training courses without hands-on activities (webinars)	3
Hackathons	2
Train-the-trainer event	1

Matching training events topics with identified training gaps

To better understand how the identified training gaps identified in Task 2.1 (see D2.1) are covered by delivered training events, we used a Gap Matching section in the [WP2 Training Inventory and Roadmap](#)¹⁴ where training event topics were matched with training gaps. Gap matching was done retrospectively because we considered training events delivered since the start of the project but gap analysis was done at a later stage. One training event could cover up to seven different gaps.

Figure 3 presents a visualisation of the gaps that were addressed by the training events delivered in the observed period. The gaps are sorted by the number of delivered training events that covered the gap. The total number of training events where the respective topic was presented is listed below the topic name (e.g. 48 of the 71 courses that were delivered had Data Management Plans as a training topic). The flag icons represent all Nodes that reported at least one delivered training event covering the topic. The number of training events where the respective topic was addressed and were organised by the specific Node is listed beside the flag icon of each Node. Note that one training event can cover more than one topic.

¹⁴ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Vu-qzbJZOhKSJeUhzF4NDIUSDzZY7FPO8y2zDs-oDP4/edit#gid=1069928084>

Figure 3: Gaps sorted by the number of delivered training events, including data about Nodes that delivered the training events (data source: [WP2 Training Inventory and Roadmap](#)¹⁵). Figure 3 shows how the identified gaps were covered by 71 observed training events and by ELIXIR Node.

Table 3 presents the number of all delivered training events in the observed period for each gap, as well as the number of delivered training events with available training materials. The cumulative number of course participants for each gap is also provided.

Table 3: Number of delivered training events for each gap (data source: [WP2 Training Inventory and Roadmap](#)¹⁶)

Gap	Number of delivered training events on DM/DS	Number of delivered DM/DS training events with available training materials	Cumulative number of participants at delivered DM/DS training events
FAIR	48	33	1748
Data management plans	46	33	1430
Data management & Data stewardship	30	15	919
Reproducibility	28	11	657

¹⁵ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Vu-qzBJZOhKSJeUhzF4NDIUSDzZY7FPO8y2zDs-oDP4/edit#gid=1069928084>

¹⁶ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Vu-qzBJZOhKSJeUhzF4NDIUSDzZY7FPO8y2zDs-oDP4/edit#gid=1069928084>

Publishing and sharing data & archiving data	24	12	981
Metadata	16	12	460
Processing and analysing	8	3	284
Finding data/data discovery	7	0	303
Infrastructure for storing and sharing data during research	7	4	318
Documentation & Organising data	5	3	103
Policies	4	4	120
ELIXIR Data Management Toolkit	3	1	60
Capturing Data/collecting data yourself	2	1	62
Ethics	1	0	68

During the General Assembly in June 2021, CONVERGE WP2 members prioritised five of the 14 identified gaps (D2.1): FAIR, Data management & Data stewardship (DM/DS), Data management plans (DMP), Reproducibility, and ELIXIR RDMkit. When the gaps are sorted by the number of training events delivered in 2020-21 (see Figure 3), the top four topics (with the highest number of delivered events) correspond to the list of WP2-prioritised topics - the only missing prioritised topic is ELIXIR RDMkit. There were significantly more training events about FAIR and DMP than Reproducibility and DM/DS. These four topics also attracted the highest cumulative number of course participants. There were only three training events about ELIXIR RDMkit even though this is a prioritised topic, likely because the RDMkit is a new development. With better collaboration between WP2 and WP3 more training events connected to RDMkit will be delivered by the end of the project and beyond. The materials for these four topics will be consolidated and developed further in specific hackathons (Task 2.2).

6. Conclusions

By the end of 2021 the partners of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project reported to WP2 (Training and Capacity Building) on 71 delivered DM/DS training events organised by 16 countries/ELIXIR Nodes with in total more than 2000 participants. This is already a remarkable outcome. Various metadata about delivered DM/DS training events were collected. For every training event the topics covered by the event were matched with the identified training gaps. With more and more delivered training events, the matching will help us to better understand the difference between the identified gaps and the topics of actual events. Better matching will enable us to optimise the alignment of the training roadmap with the training needs.

Training events that covered the topics FAIR and Data Management Plans had the highest total number of participants, followed by Data Management & Data Stewardship, and Reproducibility. More effort is needed to support organisation and dissemination of capacity building activities to Nodes that have not yet reported any training events. This issue will be addressed through monthly WP2 community meetings and 1-2-1 meetings with selected Nodes.

Work has started to organise training material generating hackathons (via T2.2) that cover the gaps prioritised by WP2 members and will result in new training materials and courses for the WP2 community. New training materials and courses will help us boost the capacity building efforts. The development of new training materials and courses is necessary not only for the well-covered training topics but also for the topics with a smaller number of delivered training events.

Training delivery is especially important for the training topics and activities that are directly connected to ELIXIR-CONVERGE, e.g. ELIXIR Research Data Management Toolkit in collaboration with WP3, Demonstrator Projects in collaboration with WP5, as well as collaboration with the new COVID-19 related WPs (WP7 to WP9).

7. Impact

The Training and Capacity building WP in CONVERGE brings together training experts and enables synergies between the different work packages in CONVERGE and beyond (see Figure 1). The impact from the Training and Capability Building programme gets stronger both at the Node level (see Table 1) and within CONVERGE where the WP2 team has engaged with the different work packages to align and link training. The development of new training materials and courses is well underway and will help us in the delivery of more training events in the next period of the project. The number of training events participants (Figure 2 and Table 1) steadily increases throughout the project. The impact will be best observed at the end of the project, when the DM Training and Capacity Building Programme are in place. The statistics from the training events observed in T2.3 will be included in Training Metrics Database (TMD), with regard to that possible inclusion of new additional features of TMD will be explored.

The impact and dissemination indicators of the Training and Capacity Building programme will be reviewed and possibly new indicators will be developed in the second half of the project. The following target indicators will continue to be measured:

- Number of DM training events organised.
- Countries where training is organised and number of training events per country.
- Number of participants receiving training.
- Feedback from training participants (short-term feedback - STF and long-term feedback - LTF will be explored).
- Number of trainers trained via the DM TtT programme.

Two new target indicators will be explored:

- Number of training events based on training materials developed by T2.2 hackathons.
- Number of gaps covered by delivered training events.

The DM Training Programme provides a structured and cohesive approach to training in the area. This will continue to improve provisioned end-products at the end of the project. Furthermore, the Train-the-Trainer programme (in collaboration with ELIXIR Training Platform Task 4) will increase the number of DM/DS trainers, ensuring a sustainability of the DM Training Programme developed by CONVERGE.

8. Next Steps

In ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 the T2.3 will continue to support the delivery of training events delivery for the courses about Data Management and Data Stewardship. The delivery of training events will be also based on new training materials developed by T2.2. The formation of development teams for these materials is already taking place. They will participate at hackathons to develop the materials. The first new materials are expected in the next six months based on the five prioritised topics (FAIR, Data Management Plans, Data Management & Data Stewardship, Reproducibility, ELIXIR RDM Toolkit).

The identified training gaps show us where the focus for training event delivery should be. However, we will not exclude special interests of the ELIXIR Nodes and communities that are involved in DM/DS in life sciences. Experts from CONVERGE WP5, WP1 and WP3 are already included in training activities and collaboration with WP7, WP8 and WP9 is starting.

We will continue to collect metadata and gap matching data about DM/DS training events through Training Inventory. Visualisation of gap matching metrics and easy access to the metrics through TeSS will be explored. In April 2022, a “CONVERGE” tag was added to the ELIXIR Training Metrics database (TMD). This will allow us to better annotate the WP2 events that are in the TMD.

The Capacity Building activities include the development of DM Train-the-Trainer courses that will increase training capacity to teach the DM Training Programme. All this will converge to the establishment and rollout of the DM Training Programme that will enable adoption of DM practices among research communities.

Finally, work has started to establish a Community of Practice (CoP) of trainers in DM/DS, both from WP2 but also from with the national Nodes. This will contribute significantly in making the connection of the WP2 work to the national activities and will also be a good step towards embedding and sustainability of the produced training materials.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

This deliverable was originally due in January 2022. A minor delay of 3 months was requested. The minor delay should not affect the overall target of the project which was extended by a further six months due to the COVID-19 outbreak.

